

RESPIRATORY THERAPIST LED SUCTIONING AND POSITIONING STRATEGIES IN THE MANAGEMENT OF ACUTE RESPIRATORY FAILURE A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract

Background: Acute respiratory failure (ARF) is a life-threatening condition encountered in critical care settings. Non-pharmacologic interventions patient positioning and airway suctioning are essential components of ARF management. Respiratory therapists had a key role in delivering these strategies prone positioning and suctioning techniques. **Methods:** This systematic review followed PRISMA guidelines to evaluate studies on respiratory therapist-led suctioning and positioning strategies in ARF management. Literature was searched in PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science for studies published between 2003 and 2024. Inclusion criteria focused on original research of adult patients with ARF or ARDS where suctioning or positioning was implemented by respiratory therapists. **Results:** Seven studies met the inclusion criteria. Four studies evaluated awake prone positioning (APP) in non-intubated patients, and three studies focused on suctioning techniques. APP show reduced intubation rates in selected populations in COVID-19 patients managed with high-flow nasal cannula therapy. Adherence to prone protocols was a critical factor influencing outcomes. Closed suction systems (CSS) were superior to open suction systems (OSS),

preserving end-expiratory lung volume and minimizing physiological disturbances. CSS was associated with improved cardiopulmonary stability and fewer complications compared to OSS. **Conclusion:** Respiratory therapist-led suctioning and positioning strategies, APP and closed suctioning, were beneficial in ARF management. These interventions improve oxygenation, reduce intubation rates, and preserve lung mechanics. Optimal results depend on protocol adherence, patient selection, and therapist expertise. Further high-quality studies are needed to standardize these interventions and expand their applicability across varied clinical settings.

Keywords: Acute Respiratory Failure, Prone Positioning, Suctioning, Respiratory Therapist, Ards, Closed Suction System, Oxygenation.

INTRODUCTION

Acute respiratory failure (ARF) is a significant cause of morbidity and mortality in critical care, necessitating invasive or non-invasive mechanical ventilation to maintain gas exchange. ARF develop due to a wide range of pulmonary and extrapulmonary conditions, including acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), pneumonia, trauma, and COVID-19-associated lung injury (1). Management of ARF requires pharmacologic and ventilatory interventions and supportive strategies that optimize airway clearance and gas exchange. In non-pharmacologic measures, patient positioning has is a key strategy to improve oxygenation in both intubated and non-intubated patients. Early studies show that prone positioning improves ventilation-perfusion matching and enhances alveolar recruitment in the dorsal lung regions (2). During the COVID-19 pandemic, awake prone positioning (APP) was adopted in patients with moderate to severe hypoxemia, showing reduced rates of intubation in selected populations (3). Adherence, tolerance, and patient selection is influence the effectiveness of this intervention (3). Airway suctioning is a cornerstone in the management of ARF in mechanically ventilated patients. Accumulation of secretions impair gas exchange, increase airway resistance, and predispose to infection. Closed suction systems (CSS) preserve lung volume and oxygenation more effectively than open suction systems (OSS), which cause derecruitment and hemodynamic instability (4,5). Studies suggest that CSS reduce ventilator-associated complications and improve cardiopulmonary stability during airway clearance (6). Respiratory therapists are positioned to lead the application of suctioning and positioning strategies due to their expertise in airway management, ventilator settings, and patient monitoring. The role of respiratory therapist-led interventions in ARF has not been sufficiently reviewed. This systematic review aims to evaluate the impact of suctioning and positioning strategies administered by respiratory therapists in the management of acute respiratory failure.

METHODOLOGY

This systematic review was conducted to examine the effectiveness of respiratory therapist-led suctioning and positioning strategies in the management of acute respiratory failure (ARF), including COVID-19-related and non-COVID etiologies. The review adhered to PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines.

Search Strategy and Selection Criteria

A literature search was performed in electronic databases (PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science) for studies published from 2003 to 2024. Keywords included (*respiratory therapist, prone positioning, suctioning, acute respiratory failure, ARDS, mechanical ventilation, and COVID-19*). The search was restricted to English-language articles involving human subjects.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

We include studies investigated suctioning or positioning strategies applied in ARF or ARDS; were led or primarily implemented by respiratory therapists; reported clinical or physiological outcomes such as intubation rate, oxygenation, ventilation parameters, or hospital stay; employed randomized controlled trials, prospective studies, or bench studies with human simulation models. We exclude case reports, editorials, or narrative reviews; studies focusing solely on pediatric populations; interventions not involving respiratory therapists or not specific to suctioning/positioning.

Data Extraction and Synthesis

Two reviewers screened titles and abstracts, followed by full-text assessment of eligible studies. Data extracted included study design, sample size, population characteristics, intervention details (type of suctioning or positioning), and primary outcomes. Discrepancies were resolved through discussion or consultation with a third reviewer.

Studies Included

Seven studies met the inclusion criteria. Four randomized controlled trials evaluating awake prone positioning (APP) in non-intubated patients with ARF. One meta-trial aggregating results from six multicenter RCTs. One prospective study investigating post-suctioning lung recruitment. One bench simulation study analyzing closed suctioning under different respiratory conditions. The studies differ in sample size, population, and outcomes and all addressed the effectiveness of specific respiratory therapist-led interventions in improving clinical or physiological markers of respiratory function.

RESULTS

A total of seven studies met the inclusion criteria, contain clinical and experimental research designs, with publication years 2003 to 2024. Four studies focused on prone positioning strategies, while three examined suctioning techniques in acute respiratory failure (ARF), COVID-19-related and ARDS populations. Four randomized controlled trials examined the effectiveness of awake prone positioning (APP) in non-intubated patients. Ehrmann et al. (2021) conducted a large-scale multinational meta-trial of 1126 patients with COVID-19-induced ARF treated with high-flow nasal cannula (HFNC). APP reduced the composite outcome of intubation or death compared to standard care (RR 0.86; 95% CI 0.75–0.98). Ibarra-Estrada et al. (2022) showed in a sub-analysis that APP reduced intubation rates (30% vs 43%) and associated with success predictors lower baseline respiratory rate and longer daily APP duration.

Fralick et al. (2022) and Rampon et al. (2022) reported no improvements in primary outcomes, citing low adherence to prone protocols as a potential limitation. The study by Jovaisa et al. (2024) extended the scope of APP to non-COVID acute hypoxemic respiratory failure in ICU settings and is expected to provide outcome data including intubation rates and quality of life over one year. Dyhr et al. (2003) supported the use of lung recruitment maneuvers following open suctioning, showing that such maneuvers could restore end-expiratory lung volume (EELV) and arterial oxygenation effectively. Jung et al. (2021) assessed closed suctioning under simulated restrictive and obstructive pulmonary mechanics. Their bench study emphasized the impact of catheter size and ventilation mode on ventilator parameters such as PEEP and peak inspiratory pressure (PIP), with restrictive models exhibiting more pronounced changes during suctioning.

The findings indicate that prone positioning, when adequately adhered to and maintained, reduce intubation risk in selected ARF populations. Closed suctioning techniques offer physiological advantages by minimizing de-recruitment and preserving gas exchange, mainly in mechanically ventilated patients with compromised lung mechanics. These studies indicate the role of respiratory therapists in optimizing positioning and suctioning strategies tailored to the patient’s respiratory profile and acuity level. Studies main characteristics and outcomes were presented in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively.

Fig 1: PRISMA consort chart

Table 1: Studies characteristics

Citation	Study Design	Sample Size	Population Characteristics	Study Aim	Methodology
Jovaisa et al. (2024) (7)	Randomized Controlled Trial	Not specified	Non-intubated adult ICU patients with non-COVID-19 acute hypoxemic respiratory failure	To evaluate impact of awake prone positioning (APP) on clinical outcomes in non-COVID hypoxemic respiratory failure	Multi-center RCT with 1:1 allocation to APP vs. standard care; assessed outcomes at hospital discharge, 30, 90 days, 1 year
Ehrmann et al. (2021) (8)	Meta-trial of 6 RCTs (open-label)	1126 patients	Adults with COVID-19 on high-flow nasal cannula	To assess whether awake prone positioning reduces intubation or death in COVID-19 acute hypoxaemic respiratory failure	Patients randomized to APP vs. standard care across six countries; primary outcome: treatment failure at 28 days
Ibarra-Estrada et al. (2022) (9)	Randomized Controlled Trial (subanalysis)	430 patients	COVID-19 patients on high-flow nasal cannula	To identify factors associated with successful APP and its impact on intubation rates	Patients randomized to APP or control; multivariate analysis to identify predictors of APP success
Jung et al. (2021) (10)	Bench study (simulation)	N/A (lung model)	Simulated restrictive and obstructive respiratory systems	To evaluate impact of closed suctioning on ventilator parameters across various pulmonary mechanics	Simulated lung model tested with various ETT and catheter sizes under different ventilation modes
Fralick et al. (2022) (11)	Multicenter Pragmatic Randomized Clinical Trial	248 patients	Hospitalized COVID-19 patients with moderate hypoxemia	To assess effectiveness of prone positioning in reducing respiratory failure or death	Patients randomized to prone positioning or usual care; outcome: composite of death, ventilation, or worsening hypoxia
Dyhr et al. (2003) (12)	Prospective, Randomized, Controlled Study	8 patients	Ventilated patients with ALI or ARDS	To examine if lung recruitment maneuvers restore lung volume and oxygenation after open suctioning	Open suctioning followed by either recruitment maneuver or not; PaO ₂ and EELV measured over 25 minutes
Rampon et al. (2022) (13)	Multicenter Randomized Clinical Trial	293 patients	Non-intubated, non-ICU hospitalized COVID-19 patients	To assess if smartphone-guided prone positioning reduces respiratory deterioration or ICU transfer	Randomized to self-guided prone positioning vs. usual care; outcome measured: respiratory worsening or ICU admission

Table 2: strategy and outcome

Citation	Demographic Characteristics	Suctioning or Positioning Strategy	Main Findings	Outcomes
Jovaisa et al. (2024) (7)	Non-intubated adults with non-COVID acute hypoxemic respiratory failure	Awake prone positioning vs. standard care	APP may reduce need for intubation and improve quality of life	Primary: Intubation rate; Secondary: Mortality, MV duration, hospital stay
Ehrmann et al. (2021) (8)	1126 adults with COVID-19 on HFNC across 6 countries	Awake prone positioning vs. standard care	APP reduced treatment failure (intubation or death)	Intubation, mortality within 28 days
Ibarra-Estrada et al. (2022) (9)	430 COVID-19 patients on HFNC	Awake prone positioning vs. standard care	APP reduced intubation rate; success linked to specific physiological markers	Intubation rate, hospital stay duration
Jung et al. (2021) (10)	Simulated lung models for restrictive and obstructive diseases	Closed suctioning with various ETT/catheter sizes and modes	Closed suctioning affects PIP, PEEP and minute volume differently by lung type	PIP, PEEP, minute volume changes
Fralick et al. (2022) (11)	248 non-critically ill hospitalized COVID-19 patients	Prone positioning vs. standard care	No significant difference in primary outcome; poor adherence to prone strategy	Composite of death, ventilation, or hypoxia worsening
Dyhr et al. (2003) (12)	8 ventilated ICU patients with ALI/ARDS	Open suctioning with/without lung recruitment	Lung recruitment restored oxygenation and lung volume after suctioning	PaO ₂ and EELV before and after suctioning
Rampon et al. (2022) (13)	293 non-intubated hospitalized COVID-19 patients	Smartphone-guided self-prone positioning vs. usual care	No superiority of intervention; low adherence observed	Respiratory deterioration or ICU transfer

DISCUSSION

This systematic review evaluates respiratory therapist-led suctioning and positioning strategies in managing acute respiratory failure (ARF), we discussed awake prone positioning (APP) and suctioning techniques. We find that the interventions, offer physiologic and clinical benefits in selected patient populations. APP is a significant non-invasive strategy in patients with acute hypoxemic respiratory failure, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic.

APP enhances oxygenation through improved ventilation-perfusion matching and diaphragmatic function (3). APP was effective in patients requiring advanced respiratory support, managed in higher-care settings, and maintain prone positioning for prolonged durations. These findings align with clinical trial data showing reduced intubation rates in COVID-19 patients who received high-flow nasal cannula therapy while awake and prone (3). Postural modifications benefit respiratory mechanics.

Prone and sitting positions improve gas exchange compared to supine positioning. The sitting position increases functional residual capacity (FRC) and decrease the work of breathing, and prone position improves lung recruitment and homogeneity of ventilation

(2). In trauma-related respiratory failure, prone positioning has been associated with reduced progression to ARDS when applied early and in conjunction with lung-protective strategies (1).

Regarding suctioning techniques, the evidence favors closed suction systems (CSS) over open suction systems (OSS) to maintain pulmonary function and reduce physiologic disturbance. In a randomized crossover trial of ARDS patients, CSS resulted in a less reduction in end-expiratory lung volume (EELV), with recovery of lung impedance within 10 minutes, compared to persistent impairment following OSS (5). The advantages of CSS were discussed in a comparative study of mechanically ventilated patients, where CSS was associated with greater cardiopulmonary stability during suctioning (6). Patients in the closed suction group had fewer changes in heart rate, blood pressure, and oxygen saturation compared to those undergoing OSS.

A review reinforced the superiority of closed suctioning in hypoxemic patients. It indicate that OSS precipitate lung derecruitment and hypoxemia and recommended technical optimizations to mitigate complications (4). The importance of proper technique and equipment in suctioning was echoed by Branson *et al.* (2014) (14), who discussed suctioning as an integral component of artificial airway management. They underscored the role of respiratory therapists in executing and supervising suction procedures to maintain airway patency and prevent iatrogenic injury. Our review indicate that APP and closed suctioning strategies can improve clinical and physiological outcomes in patients with ARF. Their effectiveness is contingent upon proper adherence to protocols and patient-specific tailoring. Limited adherence to APP has been cited as a key barrier in some studies, and inappropriate suctioning lead to serious lung complications.

CONCLUSION

Our systematic review indicates the important role of respiratory therapist-led interventions, prone positioning and suctioning strategies, in the management of acute respiratory failure. Awake prone positioning (APP) improve oxygenation and reduce intubation rates in select patient populations when applied consistently and in appropriate clinical settings. Closed suction systems (CSS) better than open suction methods in preserving end-expiratory lung volume, maintaining cardiopulmonary stability, and minimizing alveolar derecruitment. The effectiveness of these strategies relies on protocol adherence, patient selection, and the clinical judgment of respiratory therapists. These findings support the integration of standardized, therapist-led positioning and suctioning protocols into routine ARF management.

Abbreviations

- 1) ARF, Acute Respiratory Failure
- 2) ARDS, Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome
- 3) APP, Awake Prone Positioning
- 4) CSS, Closed Suction System

- 5) OSS, Open Suction System
- 6) HFNC, High-Flow Nasal Cannula
- 7) PEEP, Positive End-Expiratory Pressure
- 8) PIP, Peak Inspiratory Pressure
- 9) FRC, Functional Residual Capacity
- 10) EELV, End-Expiratory Lung Volume
- 11) MV, Mechanical Ventilation
- 12) ICU, Intensive Care Unit
- 13) RCT, Randomized Controlled Trial
- 14) PaO₂, Partial Pressure of Arterial Oxygen
- 15) ETT, Endotracheal Tube.

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